

Set of 40 studies of different patients

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Contact info.: <https://chameleon.eu/#contact>

Studies count: 40

Subjects count: 40

Age range: Between 54 years and 86 years

Sex: Male, Female

Body part(s): ABDOMEN, CHEST, COLOSCANNER, LUNG, SPINE, TAP, Unknown

Modality: CT